

An Empirical Investigation of Entrepreneurial Orientation, Social Capital, Entrepreneurial Motivation and Value Creation: The Mediating Role of Entrepreneurial Intention

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Abstract

In the present world, SMEs mostly face trouble meeting the challenges of today's globally competitive marketplace as they lack sufficient versatility, technology, entrepreneurial knowledge and entrepreneurial intention throughout the business life cycle. This paper proposes a theoretical and practical framework based on a literature review and primary data analysis to understand and develop an entrepreneurial culture in Pakistani SMEs. The aim is to clarify the concept of entrepreneurial intention (EI) through a conceptual model developed by proposing antecedents of entrepreneurial intention (EI) in an integrated framework examining their impact on the theory of planned behaviour (TPB) to boost organisational value creation. This research paper contributes to TPB by proposing thoughtful hypotheses based on empirical results. Using PLS-SEM, our theoretical model is tested on a sample of 301 entrepreneurs in the Sports and Textile sector of Pakistani SMEs. Data is collected from the managers/owners of those entrepreneurial firms already existing in the market to gain better insights into the development of organisational value creation through EI. The results revealed that the best predictors for EI are antecedents like entrepreneurial orientation, social capital and entrepreneurial motivation that impact attitudes, subjective norms and PBC, respectively, of TPB to enhance EI. In addition, results confirmed that EI mediated the relationship between entrepreneurial orientation, social capital and entrepreneurial motivation for improving organisational value creation. In conclusion, the factors identified in this research study can act as a prime variable for management implications to achieve SMEs' longevity. The study also discussed theoretical and practical implications and research limitations.

Keywords: Entrepreneurial Intention, Entrepreneurial Motivation, Entrepreneurial Orientation, Social Capital, Value Creation, SMEs.

1. Introduction

SMEs are pivotal in economic growth and development around the globe. They are central in meeting the demand of niche markets. Their importance doubles in developing countries like Pakistan, where income, employment generation, production and exports become a dire need for the nation. In Pakistan, more than 5 million SMEs account for 40% contribution to GDP. This sector contributes 78% of non-agribusiness sector employment. (SMEDA, 2019). These enterprises are spread all over Pakistan, yet most SMEs lag quality manufactured products due to the continued reliance on traditional technologies, the absence of coherent rules/policies, high transaction costs and loan unavailability (SBP, 2022). Furthermore, Covid -19 adversely impacted the actions taken to meet the demanding financial and socio-cultural crunch (Shafi et al., 2020).

According to the literature review, studies emphasised continued participation from entrepreneurs in dealing with SMEs' long-term sustainability issues. Researchers revealed that intentions are pivotal to creating new entrepreneurial business strategies that drive economic prosperity and foster sustainability (Ajzen, 2019; La Barbera & Ajzen, 2020). Entrepreneurial intention is related to an individual's mental process that leads to the planning and implementation of business plans (Ajzen, 1991; Kautonen et al., 2015). According to the literature review, most studies emphasised the development of the three prime determinants of the theory of planned behaviour (TPB), including attitudes, subjective norms and PBC to upsurge level of entrepreneurial intention (EI). Nevertheless, primarily, the results are inconsistent in understanding the predictors of EI, particularly in underdeveloped countries like Pakistan, where several psychological, sociological and economic factors hinder the development of EI in the practical world, as mentioned by the academicians (Arshad et al., 2016; Mahfud et al., 2020). Despite the growing importance of entrepreneurial activity and focus on implementation plans in Pakistan, very few academicians worked on SMEs' entrepreneurial and strategic choices (SMEDA, 2019).

Therefore, this research paper intends to study the factors affecting entrepreneurial intention (EI) within established SMEs, given how the entrepreneurial intentions relate to new value creation through the enrichment of entrepreneurial attitudes, subjective norms and perceived behavioural control as elaborated in TPB (Krueger et al., 2000; Bernardus et al., 2020). Value creation is a fundamental attribute of firms to exploit new and existing markets and creates organisational longevity (Fini et al., 2012). The proposed causal antecedents of EI based on sociological and psychological studies include entrepreneurial orientation, entrepreneurial motivation and social capital. No previous studies have jointly considered antecedents and consequences of EI at the organisational level. The methodology included structural equation modelling (SEM) techniques tested on a sample of 301 entrepreneurial managers/owners in the manufacturing sector of Textile and Sports SMEs of Pakistan.

The results revealed a positive relationship among the proposed variables. Thus, inducing the need to understand the proposed antecedents for EI creation at the SMEs level. This study contributes to the literature on corporate entrepreneurship by expanding the TPB by exploring antecedents which impact the attitude, subjective norms and PBC, which are the immediate predictors of EI and help boost firm value creation. The findings also supported hypotheses that entrepreneurial intention mediated the relationship between entrepreneurial orientation, social capital and entrepreneurial

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motivation for enhancing organisational value creation. The rest of the paper is structured as follows: The literature review discusses EI within established SMEs. The impact of proposed antecedents on the three central dimensions of TPB and EI for value creation. The third section narrates the research design and methodology, followed by the results and their discussion in the fourth section. The last section deals with theoretical and practical implications and research limitations.

2. Literature Review

2.1. Theoretical Background of Entrepreneurial Intention

Modern writers in management and business have presented a wide range of theories to understand entrepreneurial intention (EI). After the publication of Shapiro's inspirational work (Shapiro and Sokol, 1982), the literature began its rapid development, opening new doors to understanding the potential value of the EI approach. A shift in the focus of EI research towards the process view at the organisational level (Tallia et al., 2014; Tshikovhi and Shambare, 2015) contributed generously towards the concept advancement. The prime example is its successful integration with various theories from social and cognitive psychology into the study of entrepreneurship.

Over the years, principally, three models served as a guide in understanding the concept of entrepreneurial intentions. These models include 1) Bird's (2015) model for executing entrepreneurial ideas, 2) Shapiro and Sokol's (1982) model of the entrepreneurial event, and 3) Ajzen's (1991, 2019) theory of planned behaviour. Empirical evidence stands with the validity of the entrepreneurial event model and the theory of planned behaviour to better understand EI implication (Kautonen, et al., 2015). The other spectrum of models related to EI formation, which ranges from the TPB entrepreneurial model – TPBEM and the social cognitive career theory – SCCT investigated in a few empirical studies (Tran and Korfflesch, 2016).

The speed of the EI process remained remarkable with the TPB (Ajzen, 2019). Since the early 19th century, many academicians and practitioners have employed EI models, confirming the concept's applicability in varied settings. Regarding business development, Mair and Noboa (2017) suggested that the intention model be based on TPB. However, despite the plethora of studies dealing with the robustness of TPB and its impact on EI in different settings, its theoretical framework is mismatched, and inconsistencies arose (Kautonen et al., 2015) scheming to rethink EI models. Ajzen (2019) claimed EI to be dead and called for a profound rethinking of research to explore multiple intention dimensions related to decision-making under uncertain situations. This interpretation calls for the development of integrative and sophisticated theoretical models linking intention-based models with the desired perspective of interaction, mediation (Barnir et al., 2011) and moderation (Barnett and Pollack, 2012) effects on the entrepreneurial intention (EI) model. The lack of categorisation and robustness in the stream of EI research demands a well-organized EI model by adapting and extending the classical TPB model (Ajzen, 2019; La Barbera & Ajzen, 2020). Therefore, this study consolidates the application of the EI model with the implication of TPB and contributes towards theoretical and practical contributions.

2.2. An Intention Model: Theory of planned behaviour (TPB)

A widely accepted theoretical approach that strongly embodies Entrepreneurial Intention (EI) and behaviour is the theory of planned behaviour (Ajzen, 1991). This theory contains three main domains explaining EI: attitudes towards behaviour, subjective norms and perceived behavioural control (PCB) recognised as EI antecedents (Ajzen, 2019; Linan and Fayolle, 2015). Attitude towards behaviour indicates the person's willingness to either become an entrepreneur or create value in the existing organisation. Subjective norms deal with the peers/group's approval towards a specific action. Lastly, PBC relates to a person's confidence in his/her abilities and the resulting perception about the ease (or difficulty) towards enacting the behaviour (La Barbera & Ajzen, 2020). Intentions indicate how devoted a person is to take a particular action.

2.2.1. Direct Antecedents of EI in Established Firms

Entrepreneurial intention (EI) is an evolving field of research. Multiple studies addressed the need to create new value within the existing business ventures and marked it as the perplexing part of the entrepreneurial process. As per TPB, the first theoretical antecedent is the attitude towards EI conceptualisation that can enhance entrepreneurial value creation (Krueger et al., 2000). Attitudes develop from behavioural beliefs that people hold about a task (positive or negative) and links to new value creation through engagement in innovative, risky and proactive actions within the established firms (Ajzen, 2019).

The second antecedents refer to the subjective norms as entrepreneurs' perception of approval about their intention towards new value creation. Subjective norms are set by the internal organisational management system that approves/disapproves of entrepreneurial attitude in their organisation. Thereby, the internal influence and corporate philosophy influence the proliferation of EI through relational trust, cognitive understanding, and structural dimensions within the organisation.

The third antecedent proposed in TPB is perceived behavioural control (PBC). PBC is the belief in the ease/difficulty level of creating organisational value through the entrepreneurial process. The concept of self-efficacy was taken into the PBC to understand behavioural control, which cannot be explained by the intention developed due to a positive attitude and subjective norms. PBC influences the choice of activities, preparations and efforts undergone during the activity. Self-efficacy affects the motivational level, need to achieve, risk-propensity, entrepreneurial resourcefulness and external environment. Studies in behavioural sciences confirmed all the three antecedents Ajzen (1991) proposed as essential indicators in defining and illustrating the EI concept (Fini et al., 2012; La Barbera & Ajzen, 2020).

The originality of this paper is that it sheds light on value creation within existing SMEs by proposing antecedents that impact the determinants of TPB to illustrate the entrepreneurial intention (EI) concept. The uniqueness of this research is that few studies in the past have considered the already working owners/managers as essential respondents to evaluate the EI process for the value creation of existing SMEs.

2.2.2. Indirect Antecedents of EI in Established Firms: Conceptual Perspective and Propositions

Entrepreneurial Intention (EI) lacks a unified definition as there is more discussion on the conceptual ground than the empirical work. EI is denoted as a construct of multi-dimensions, including novel decision-making, risk-taking and consistent focus on actions irrespective of contextual complications. The actions of an entrepreneur are driven by the solid intention to create value (Sengupta, 2017). Contemporary scholars are more interested in understanding EI's concurrent missions of achieving financial and organisational value creation virtues.

To advance our knowledge of EI, this research paper proposed a set of antecedents to explain their impact more comprehensively. In compliance with Bird's (2015) intuition model, both cognitive and structural factors play a vital role in EI development; this paper labelled the direct antecedents of EI, like attitude, PBC and subjective norms, as inner or macro-domains. It proposed antecedents as the outer domains to elaborate the concept under investigation (Fini et al., 2012). As our sample was taken from organisational managers, this research assisted in understanding organisational structure towards entrepreneurial action and beliefs (Krueger et al., 2000). The following proposed sub-categories are explained as follows.

2.2.2.1. Entrepreneurial Orientation (EO) and Entrepreneurial Intention (EI) in SMEs

For a small firm, it is hard to imagine that it may take advantage of an opportunity without evolving entrepreneurial behaviour over time (Koe, 2016). Small firm growth helps understand the entrepreneurial process (Davidsson and Naldi, 2010). According to Storey (1994), entrepreneurial intention is based on entrepreneurial orientation (EO), small firms' characteristics and developmental strategies. But the strategic choices which influence SMEs' value creation depend on how the dimensions of Entrepreneurial Orientation impact the firm?

Studies linked entrepreneurial knowledge with EO to contribute to opportunity recognition. Based on that, many extant studies found entrepreneurial education and training a critical factor in developing an individual's competencies to become an entrepreneur. Other authors argued that entrepreneurial education only impacts the development of individuals' EO but cannot provoke actions if they lack the intentions (Yurtkoru et al., 2014). Thus, giving rise to inconsistency in understanding entrepreneurial orientation (EO).

Another gap in the literature is that researchers mostly used student samples rather than actual entrepreneurs' samples to understand the EI process. This is why most organisations fail to create value in the later stages of the business cycle and ultimately collapse (Davidsson and Naldi, 2010). In addition, authors who tested EO on working adults concluded that such firms are influenced mainly by three factors of EO, namely innovativeness, risk-taking and proactiveness. Conversely, the other two factors of EO (autonomy and competitive aggressiveness) didn't show a positive relationship with EI (Koe, 2016). Yet, some studies revealed a positive influence of only two EO factors (proactiveness and risk-taking) on EI and rejected the other three dimensions when tested at the organisational managers (Mkalama et al., 2020). Such conflicting results create inconsistencies with using EO to understand EI at the corporate level. According to (Birley, 1994), the reasons to start a business don't help predict the subsequent size or growth of the company. Therefore, it is essential to understand EI at the later stage of business to forecast an existing firm's growth and value creation. Scholars are more interested in finding the relationship between EO and EI constructs at the organisational level and its coherent impact on TPB. Therefore, this study adds to the body of literature by addressing the gaps mentioned above and proposes the following hypothesis:

Hypothesis 1a: In existing SMEs, the stronger the entrepreneurial orientation, the more positive the entrepreneurial attitude towards entrepreneurial intention.

Hypothesis 1b: Entrepreneurial intention mediates the relationship between entrepreneurial orientation and organisational value creation.

2.2.2.2. Social Capital (SC) and Entrepreneurial Intention (EI) in SMEs

In many parts of the world, community solidarity and mutual support are emphasised. Social capital (SC) is integral to organisational and community development. (1997) extended the model proposed by (Moran and Ghoshal, 1996) to explain how SC facilitates value creation in firms. They identified three key dimensions of social capital (SC) which include the structural (social interaction), cognitive (shared vision) and relational (trust and trustworthiness) aspects. The literature revealed that SC plays a prominent role in developing EI towards forming a conducive organisational culture based on mutual success (Audretsch and Aldridge, 2012). However, entrepreneurs' role in creating SC has not been analysed much (Hasan, 2005). Conversely, other authors rate social capital as critical for entrepreneurial intention (EI) development (Gilmeanu & Gauca, 2017). Yet, some authors mentioned the negative impact of social capital (SC) on performance and entrepreneurial outcomes. These mixed results proposed the need to recheck the link between SC, TPB and EI and their relative impact on organisational value creation (Salamzadeh, 2022). From this point of view, it will be more interesting to find out the overlapping between levels of SC and managers' EI in the value creation process.

Hypothesis 2a: In existing SMEs, the stronger the social capital, the more positive impact of subject norms on entrepreneurial intention.

Hypothesis 2b: Entrepreneurial intention mediates the relationship between social capital and organisational value creation.

2.2.2.3. Entrepreneurial Motivation and Entrepreneurial Intention (EI) in SMEs

The need to understand motivation at different levels of the organisation is as pivotal as any other element for the success of the enterprise. Within the organisation, the entrepreneurs and the organisational culture impact on the motivational level of the whole organisation. According to the TPB, the level of motivation plays an integral part towards entrepreneurial

attitude within organisations (Fini et al., 2012). Two sets of motivational dimensions identified by the academicians include the “general entrepreneurial motivations” and the “task-specific entrepreneurial motivations” (Shane et al., 2003). The task-specific motivation is preferred as it depends on the need for achievement (McClelland, 1961), tolerance for ambiguity (Bandura, 1982), locus of control and external environmental control (Senen and Sidharta, 2016). This type of motivation is a better predictor of entrepreneurial intention (EI) in the organisation than the general motivational level (Baum and Locke, 2004). Defining the entrepreneurs’ characters and linking them to the specific task motivation presents a gap in the research area (Fini et al., 2012). The concept that specifies motivational behaviour which can predict EI demands justifications for its validation. Supporting the idea that entrepreneurial motivation predicts behavioural control towards EI and improves organisation value creation leads to the following hypothesis:

Hypothesis 3a: In exiting SMEs, the stronger the entrepreneurial motivation, the more positive impact of perceived behavioural control on EI.

Hypothesis 3b: EI mediates the relationship between entrepreneurial motivation and organisational value creation.

2.2.2.4. Linkage between EI and Value Creation (VC) in SMEs

Value creation (VC) is a widely discussed topic when describing entrepreneurial intention (Kraus et al., 2013). However, it is mainly defined and measured in the literature at the individual level. Few research studies measuring value creation (VC) at the organisational level revealed how efficiently and effectively organisations produce and offer their products (Ajiro, 2015). Value creation (VC) is a multifaceted phenomenon which needs further investigation of its interactions with entrepreneurial intention (EI) at the organisational level (Rispaal and Servantie, 2018). Another gap found in the literature is that VC is more inclined towards revealing the impact of external stakeholders like customers, suppliers and investors as a unit of analysis rather than the internal ones like individual employees, managers, products/service or organisations (Bowman, 2010).

There are plethora of researches on entrepreneurial intention (EI) and value creation (Kraus et al., 2013), yet, the need to define the link between EI and organisational value creation requires further justifications. To understand the configuration of beliefs and desires in EI to create new value in an existing firm, we need to consider the amount of uncertainty the organisation is willing to endure (Mcmullen and Shepherd, 2013). Consequently, if the focus is towards understanding the behaviour for firm, there is a greater likelihood that the organisation will generate and develop value creation (VC) more effectively than firms where EI is not given due attention (Gielnik et al., 2010). Based on the above discussion, this study aimed to check the impact of EI as defined in TPB on firm value creation (VC) in the SMEs of Pakistan.

Hypothesis 4: In existing SMEs, the stronger the entrepreneurial intention, the more positive impact on organisational value creation.

2.3. Conceptual Framework

Based on the prospective research studies, the conceptual and theoretical gaps as discussed in this paper, especially in the context of Pakistani SMEs, calls for a need to develop a theoretical framework to analyse and extend the concept of entrepreneurial intention in the context of TPB (Tallia et al., 2022).

Figure1: Proposed Conceptual Model

Therefore, this research study proposes a causal linkage between social capital (SC), entrepreneurial motivation, entrepreneurial orientation (EO) and entrepreneurial intention (EI), as depicted in Figure 1 below. This figure shows that Entrepreneurial Intention as defined in the context of TPB will be an outcome of proposed antecedents. Subsequently, Entrepreneurial Intention will mediate the relationship between the proposed antecedents and Organisational Value Creation.

3. Research Methodology

This research study used the survey method for gathering data as it is one of the reliable techniques to investigate and explore human behaviour (Bryman and Bell, 2022). Self-administered questionnaires are preferred to obtain responses from the owners/managers of Pakistani SMEs to cover a wide geographical area and kept respondents' identities enclosed to ensure valid responses. The questionnaire contained well-structured questions which are easy to understand and are measured using the Likert scale (Bryman and Bell, 2022). SMEs in the textile and sports industry (Pakistan) made up the population of this study. Finalization of the firms and their managers through the random sampling method was a challenging procedure. The selected firms are mainly obtained from the Punjab region in the East of Pakistan. Punjab region is characterised as the hub of the industrial sector where clusters of SMEs are working using efficient and high-tech operational processes. The list of the industries is obtained from SMEDA and Sialkot and Textile Chamber of Commerce, Pakistan. Only those firms in Sports and Textile industries are selected which are based on entrepreneurial concepts for organisational development and sustainability. So, the final sample accounts for 301 questionnaires in the data collection procedure in which managers/owners gave a valid and complete response to all the questions. Finally, this research employed a method of PLS-SEM to examine and report the PLS-SEM path's results (Hair et al., 2014).

4. Findings/Results

4.1. Findings of Descriptive Statistics

As per the findings in Table 1, out of the 301 responses, the age of the respondents mainly lied in the range of 36-45 years (Mean: 3.3721; SD: 1.10804); graduate level of education 4.0365 (SD 1.13519), level of experience in between the range of 6-10 years (M: 3.6478) and mostly males 1.1728 (SD: 0.47264). Most responses were collected from the textile firms 3.0465 (SD: 1.69051) with the firm age 3.2326 (SD: 1.17150).

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics

Background characteristics of SME Owners/Managers					
	N	Mean	SD	Minimum	Maximum
Age	301	3.3721	1.10804	1.00	5.00
Education	301	4.0365	1.13519	2.00	6.00
Experience	301	3.6478	1.20923	1.00	5.00
Designation	301	3.5615	1.40251	1.00	6.00
Gender	301	1.1728	.47264	1.00	4.00
Characteristic of SME					
Department	301	2.1661	1.04832	1.00	4.00
Industry	301	3.0465	1.69051	1.00	5.00
Ownership	301	2.5382	.78488	1.00	4.00
Employees	301	3.2259	1.18973	1.00	5.00
Firm age	301	3.2326	1.17150	1.00	5.00
Business	301	1.8073	.75900	1.00	3.00

4.2. Results of Instrument Validity

The instrument's validity is measured by estimating the value of composite reliability (CR), which, if higher than 0.60 and statistically significant, is considered a valid test towards item reliability (Wolf et al., 2013). As given in Table. 2, all the items showed composite reliability (CR) values above 0.90 which confirmed the high validity level of the selected instrument.

Table 2: Predictor Measures

Domain and predictor	Item	Scale format	Research reference	CR
Entrepreneurial Orientation	11	1-5 Likert scale	Covin and Slevin (1990), based on the work of Miller and Friesen (1982)	0.934
Social Capital	14	1-5 Likert scale	Nahapiet and Ghoshal (1998)	0.943
Entrepreneurial Motivation	18	1-5 Likert scale	Taomina and Lao (2007) and Jayawarna et al., (2013)	0.951
Entrepreneurial Intention	9	1-7 Likert scale	Fini et al. (2012)	0.955
Organizational Value Creation	12	1-5 Likert scale	Alibeyki and Khosravi, 2014	0.935

Source: Author

4.3. Results of Correlation

The correlations table as shown (in table 3) below, depicted an appreciable high positive correlation among the variables.

Table 3: Correlation

	Mean	SD	EO	SC	EM	EI	VC
Entrepreneurial Orientation (EO)	3.09	.904	0.922				
Social Capital (SC)	3.70	.703	.529**	0.935			
Entrepreneurial Motivation (MO)	3.51	.859	.553**	.573**	0.945		
Entrepreneurial Intention (EI)	4.00	1.46	.644**	.551**	.582**	0.946	
Value Creation (VC)	3.42	.909	.578**	.526**	.575**	.721**	0.924

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

4.4. Structural Model

The structure model presents excellent measures of goodness of fit, as shown in figure 2 below. The empirical model fully supports the effectiveness of the proposed antecedents in predicting entrepreneurial intention (EI) in SMEs. The results revealed that all the proposed antecedents effectively supported the EI and the resultant impact of EI on value creation (VC), as depicted in the figure below. Thereby supporting all the proposed hypotheses.

Figure 2: Structural Model

4.5. Mediation Analysis

The mediation analysis was performed to check the impact of the mediator (i.e., entrepreneurial intention, EI) while describing the relationship between the given antecedents: entrepreneurial orientation (EO), entrepreneurial motivation (EM) and social capital (SC) on organisational value creation (VC). The results (as shown in Table 4) depicted that the indirect path of EM and EI (where H4a: $\beta = 0.267$, $t = 2.705$, $p < 0.001$) and EO and EI (where H2a: $\beta = 0.406$, $t = 4.903$, $p < 0.001$) were significant. Thus, supporting Hypothesis, H1a and H2a Also, the indirect path of SC and EI (where H3a: $\beta = 0.180$, $t = 2.854$, $p = 0.001$) was significant, thereby accepting H3a. Our results revealed that EI partially mediates the impact of EO (where H2b: $\beta = 0.298$, $t = 4.687$, $p < 0.001$) and EM (where H4b: $\beta = 0.196$, $t = 2.652$, $p < 0.001$) on organizational value creation (VC) whereas EI also mediates the impact of SC on VC (where H3b: $\beta = 0.132$, $t = 2.788$, $p > 0.001$). Hence, supporting H1b and H2b and H3b. The results (as shown in Table 4) illustrated that the direct impact of EI and VC (where H5: $\beta = 0.733$, $t = 2.466$, $p < 0.001$) was also significant. Thus, supporting H4.

The results, as depicted below in table 4, represented that the best predictors for EI are exogenous dimensions of TPB and the antecedents that effect the TPB dimensions to promote EI are EO, SC and EM. Moreover, EI serves as a mediator between the proposed antecedents and organisational value creation and promote organisation longevity and sustainability.

Table 4: Test of Mediation

Hypothesis	Beta	SE	T-Value	P-Values
EM -> EI	0.267	0.096	2.705	0.000***
EO -> EI	0.406	0.082	4.903	0.000***
SC -> EI	0.180	0.068	2.854	0.001**
EI -> VC	0.733	0.036	2.466	0.000***
Mediation				
EM -> EI -> VC	0.196	0.072	2.652	0.000***
EO -> EI -> VC	0.298	0.063	4.687	0.000***
SC -> EI -> VC	0.132	0.051	2.788	0.006**

p < .05; * = p < .01; ** = p < .00***

5. Discussion

This research paper was based on understanding the need to develop, plan and design entrepreneurial activities by promoting entrepreneurial intention (EI) in the existing SMEs. It investigated key antecedents that promote EI, particularly in the established SMEs of Pakistan. Our results illustrated that all the proposed hypotheses regarding the inclusion of antecedents and checking the role of EI as a mediator were accepted and revealed a significant impact on EI process. According to this research study, antecedents like entrepreneurial orientation (EO) and entrepreneurial motivation (EM) positively related to EI validated in the light of the TPB attitudes and perceived behavioural control dimensions, respectively. Moreover, social capital (SC) also exhibited its impact on EI by influencing the subjective norms as proposed in TPB. When checking the mediating impact of EI on the relationship between EO and VC the results were significant. The positive effect of EO (risk, proactiveness and innovativeness) was the accurate depiction of entrepreneurial attitudes to grow and excel. Likewise, the mediating role of EI between EM and VC was supported depicting that entrepreneurial motivational factors triggered the perceived behaviour control and elevated the entrepreneurial intention (EI) help promote organisational value creation, as proposed in the previous studies (Shane et al., 2003). Lastly, as social capital also revealed a significant relationship between EI and value creation, where EI was taken as mediator suggested that the reliance on the social network was favoured by the managers, who experience strong social ties, values, governmental support, education and training and monitoring system in the Sports and the Textile sector of Pakistan. However, the findings may vary depending on the industry, management system and organisational culture. The subjective norms depicted cognitive behaviour necessary to implement entrepreneurial actions. Future studies can work on exploring factors through theoretical and empirical points of view that could provoke the development of such behavioural attitudes to improvise entrepreneurial support and implementation in a better way. Such actions would aid SMEs to grow and sustain in the market for long. Lastly, from the theoretical viewpoint, checking the same antecedents in different industrial settings and with other antecedents can expand the understanding base.

6. Theoretical Contribution

This study makes several theoretical contributions and suggests how to extend the Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB). As proposed by Ajzen (2019; La Barbera & Ajzen, 2020), there is a need to add more variables to the theory to explain the entrepreneurial intention and to deal with inconsistent results (Kautonen, et al., 2015). To enhance entrepreneurial intention, this research study introduced antecedents like entrepreneurial orientation, social capital and entrepreneurial motivation to check how they impacted the three prime determinants of TPB which are attitudes, subjective norms and PBC. Some scholars suggested that organisational orientation towards entrepreneurship help mould attitudes and regulate intentions (Lee and Peterson, 2000). TPB endorses entrepreneurial orientation as an antecedent that can impact entrepreneurial intention (Koe, 2016). This research confirms to the theory of TPB by revealing a positive relationship between Entrepreneurial Orientation on Entrepreneurial Intention. Moreover, it extends the relationship and took EI as a mediator between EO and organisational value creation and exhibited a significant relationship in the context of SMEs of Pakistan. Correspondingly, a positive relationship was found between the entrepreneurial motivation and entrepreneurial intention where entrepreneurial motivation impacts on the PBC to enhance entrepreneurial intention. In addition, this research extends the theory and checked the mediating role of EI between social capital and organisational value creation and found significant results. Thus, this study extends previous research that confirmed a direct link between attitudes and PBC on entrepreneurial intention (Krueger et al., 2000; Sarwar et al., 2021). The relationship between social capital and entrepreneurial intention also revealed a positive effect and influenced social norms to enhance entrepreneurial intention. Furthermore, entrepreneurial intention does mediate the relationship between social capital and organisational value creation. Thus, supporting the ideas of those authors who claim that social capital influences SMEs' performance (Daud and Yusoff, 2010). Hence the research findings offered evidence that all the three dimensions of TPB (Ajzen, 1991) can be influenced with the application of proposed antecedents to provoke entrepreneurial intention for organisational value creation in the SMEs of Pakistan.

7. Practical Implications

The outcomes of this research study have multiple practical implications for policymakers and SME owners to ensure SMEs sustainability. Firstly, this study is a straightforward guide to existing SMEs struggling in the economy to survive.

Managers should opt for strategies for new value creation to strengthen organisational sustainability (SMEDA, 2019). According to this research findings, entrepreneurial motivation is an essential predictor of entrepreneurial intention in Pakistan's SMEs managers/owners. These results are consistent with the previous research, those that emphasised the need to enhance employee motivation (Senen and Sidharta, 2016). Thereby, organisations need to focus on specific tasks, risk propensity, self-efficacy and control on impact of external environment to promote employee motivation (Nahapiet and Ghoshal, 1998). SMEs, need to focus on boosting entrepreneurial motivation to enhance employees perceived behavioural control to stimulate entrepreneurial intention. Additionally, as entrepreneurial orientation positively impacts the entrepreneurial intentions, the policymakers need to provoke such initiatives in the organisations through education and training programs to improve managers' confidence to apply creative thoughts for organisational value creation (Alibeyki and Khosravi, 2014). Likewise, as social capital supported entrepreneurial intention development. It is vital that organizational should enhance relational, cognitive and structural dimensions to provoke organizational social capital (Daud and Yusoff, 2010).

This article is novel in discussing the entrepreneurial intention concept within established SMEs as it suggests re-value creation in an existing business to gain longevity (Fini et al., 2012). To address the problem of SMEs failure after a few years of existence around the globe and particularly in Pakistan (SMEDA, 2019). The findings of this research present a great model to consult in enhancing the entrepreneurial intention of SMEs employees. Our findings align with (Kraus et al., 2013) that entrepreneurial intention plays a significant role in organisational value creation and performance enhancement. We, therefore, recommend that government policymakers and SME owners to support entrepreneurial orientation, social capital and entrepreneurial motivation to upsurge entrepreneurial attitudes, subjective norms and PBC vital for EI development to boost organisation value creation and sustainability.

8. Limitations

Nevertheless, efforts are made in designing the research, yet this study lags in some domains. First, we conducted an exploratory and cross-sectional study to obtain consistent results. However, results can't be generalised. Secondly, despite forming a conceptual model upon a solid theoretical foundation, the second insignificant consequence of cross-sectional study is the diversity of age and entrepreneurial background that can affect the investigation results. A longitudinal study will be adequate to tackle such issues in future studies. Moreover, the proposed model is limited to mature SMEs as it suggests re-value creation in an existing business to gain longevity (Fini et al., 2012). Therefore, the results cannot be generalised on MNCs or the newly established business sector. For the corporate sector, revising the proposed model to obtain reliable results would be mandatory.

The literature also highlighted the importance of entrepreneurial orientation (EO) as a strong antecedent in determining entrepreneurial intention. Yet, this study model deliberately leaves out some factors used to determine the EI concept. For instance, based on Bandura's (1977) psychosocial factors like self-efficacy and outcome expectations, the previous studies have emphasised using these determinants as predictive variables of entrepreneurial behaviour (Hoda et al., 2021). Ajzen's theory (1991) is widely used and applied to examine the effects of perceived behavioural control (i.e., self-efficacy). This study attempts to advance the entrepreneurial self-efficacy belief by considering its sources as discussed in the theory of planned behaviour (TPB). Moreover, as literature review revealed contrasting results with different measures of Entrepreneurial Orientation to determine its impact on Entrepreneurial Intention. This study employed only three EO constructs as developed by Covin and Slevin (1990), including innovativeness, risk-taking and proactiveness which are more reliable in carrying out results (Kemelgor, 2002), whereas the aggressive and competitive behaviour doesn't fit in the context of SMEs (Koe, 2016). As the research purpose was to operationalise EO for more consistent results. Future studies can address these limitations to obtain better results.

9. Conclusion

This paper attempts to propose a novel framework illustrating how proposed constructs can influence EI development in the SMEs. The three proposed antecedents influenced the three dimensions of TPB to boost EI within the exiting SMEs of Pakistan. The results were also significant when entrepreneurial intention (EI) was taken as a mediator between the proposed antecedents and organisational value creation. Thus, supporting all the hypotheses as proposed in this research. Future researchers can empirically test this model in other countries, particularly developing ones, and across varied organisations to obtain generalised results. It would be worthwhile to explore the differences in entrepreneurial intention, entrepreneurial orientation, social capital and motivation among SMEs and their resultant impact on organisational value creation. Moreover, longitudinal studies based on the proposed conceptual model would result in conspicuous results and invaluable contributions to the academic literature of entrepreneurial and organisational development. For that reason, the proposed framework in this paper attempts to direct the academicians to re-considering these critical linkages and theory extension.

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